

FEATURES OF WORKING WITH YOUTH IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

Sultonova Latofat Sa'dullaevna

Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti
"Ijtimoiy fanlar" kafedrası katta o'qituvchisi
E-mail: sultonovalatofat@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this article, no matter how much we appreciate the positive role of globalization in turning the achievements in the field of science, technology, and technology into the property of the peoples of the world, we cannot ignore the fact that inequality is emerging in this process. It was analyzed that the development of the country directly depends not only on the intelligence, knowledge and skills of the young generation of hardworking citizens, but also on their health and physical fitness.

Keywords: Globalization, education, national-ideological education, idea and ideology, patience-satisfaction, mass culture, social-humanities, patriotism, world community, sustainable development, national culture.

GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA YOSHLAR BILAN ISHLASHNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI: AN'ANAVIYLIK VA ZAMONAVIYLIK

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada bugungi kunda globallashuvning fan, texnika, texnologiya sohasidagi yutuqlarni butun dunyo xalqlari mulkiga aylantirishdagi ijobiy rolini qanchalik yuqori baholamaylik, bu jarayonda tengsizlikning vujudga kelayotganini ham e'tibordan chetda qoldira olmaymiz. Yurtni rivojlantirish yosh avlodni mehnatkash fuqarolarning nafaqat aql-idroki, bilimi va malakasi, balki ularning salomatligiga, jismoniy barkamolligiga ham bevosita bog'liq ekanligi tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Globallashuv, ta'lim, milliy-mafkuraviy tarbiya, g'oya va mafkura, sabr-qanoat, ommaviy madaniyat, ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar, vatanparvarlik, jahon hamjamiyati, barqaror taraqqiyot, milliy madaniyat.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАБОТЫ С МОЛОДЕЖЬЮ В СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ: ТРАДИЦИИ И СОВРЕМЕННОСТЬ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье, как бы мы ни ценили положительную роль глобализации в превращении достижений в области науки, техники и технологий в собственность народов мира, мы не можем игнорировать тот факт, что возникает неравенство. в этом процессе. Проанализировано, что развитие страны напрямую зависит не только от интеллекта, знаний и умений молодого поколения трудолюбивых граждан, но и от их здоровья и физической подготовленности.

Ключевые слова: Глобализация, образование, национально-идеологическое воспитание, идея и идеология, терпение-удовлетворение, массовая культура, социально-гуманитарные науки, патриотизм, мировое сообщество, устойчивое развитие, национальная культура.

At present, by improving the continuous education system, great attention is being paid to the preparation of personnel who are mature in all aspects, capable of independent thinking, strong-willed, and able to meet the requirements of the times. We have created a legal-normative basis for reforming the personnel training and continuing education system. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor Shirinboy Olimov's opinion about the need to pay attention to the issues for the further development of the continuous education system is noteworthy: "Educational reform has become a social, economic and pedagogical necessity for our country. Its implementation based on the advanced traditions of world education is considered beneficial in all respects. Reforms are a large-scale social, economic, political and pedagogical problem that covers all links of the continuous education system - ideological, organizational - pedagogical content, goal forms and methods.

In our opinion, the following are the important factors for the development of the secondary vocational education system:

- Taking into account the interest of applicants to higher education institutions that prepare teachers - pedagogues;
- Increasing the effectiveness of the educational process in higher education institutions that prepare pedagogical personnel;
- Regular improvement of the qualifications of pedagogical staff working in the system of secondary special, vocational training. It is appropriate to dwell on this issue in more detail."

Nowadays, globalization serves the general development on the one hand, and on

the other hand, it serves to accelerate the introduction of "mass culture". This creates a risk of devaluation of customs, traditions and values that are valuable for the nation.

No matter how much we appreciate the positive role of globalization in turning the achievements in the field of science, technology, and technology into the property of the peoples of the whole world, we cannot ignore the fact that inequality is emerging in this process. On the one hand, this is reflected in differences in the economic, social and political spheres between developed countries and less developed countries, or countries that are now on the path to development. The possession of the available economic resources by the highly developed countries leads to an increase in the desire to acquire the intellectual and thereby ensure their dominance, on the other hand, through the means of ensuring this dominance, their own ideas, are intensifying the popularization of their ideologies and worldviews.

Globalization, which manifests itself brightly today, has several centuries of roots. Geographical discoveries in the 15th-17th centuries brought many countries and regions into the sphere of international trade, and the industrial revolution created an economic basis for the further strengthening and widening of general relations. In later periods, such relations deepened. By the beginning of the 20th century, this process, which acquired a new qualitative character and covered all spheres of social life, began to be expressed through the concept of globalization.

In everyday life, it is common to understand globalization as a problem of universal importance. Such an understanding is one-sided, cannot reveal its essence and leads to the interpretation of globalization only as a negative phenomenon. However, in the most general sense, globalization, on the one hand, means that a certain phenomenon, process covers all regions, countries and the whole Earth, and on the other hand, it means that they affect the fate of mankind.

In particular, as the President noted, "strengthening of integration and cooperation between states and peoples, creation of facilities for foreign investments, capital and goods, free movement of labor force, creation of many new jobs, modern communication and information the rapid spread of technologies and scientific achievements, the harmonization of different values on a universal basis, the acquisition of a new quality of intercivilizational communication, the increase of opportunities for mutual assistance during environmental disasters - of course, all this is achieved due to globalization."

Today, different aspects of globalization are distinguished in the scientific literature. First of all, it is necessary to note the existence of demographic and ecological problems, which represent issues related to the stress of nature, meeting the needs of food, drinking water and similar needs in the conditions of rapid population growth.

Globalization of the technosphere, which does not recognize any national boundaries and characterizes the emergence of a common technological and information space in the world, is another characteristic of it.

At the same time, it is necessary not to forget that political globalization and socio-cultural globalization representing processes in the field of science, culture, education and ethics, as well as ideological globalization related to ideological influence, propaganda and agitation are also taking place. .

The process of globalization has fundamentally changed the world ideological landscape, created new goals and directions of geopolitics. As a result of this, on the one hand, the methods and methods of inculcating various ideas into people's minds have improved, and on the other hand, the possibilities of protecting citizens from the influence of inhumane ideas have decreased. As a result of the collapse of the Soviet Union and socio-political events in other regions of the world, there is a great threat to the security of countries that have gained independence. For this reason, it is becoming necessary to study the ideological image of the present time in order to have comprehensive information about the nature of the ideological pressures applied to the countries that have gained independence.

When it comes to the role of ideology in the implementation of geostrategic goals, in order to understand the essence of the matter, it is necessary to pay attention to the following situation, which is related to the relationship between ideas and consciousness. A certain idea may not be accepted by a person or it may remain in a person's mind only as certain information. In the first case, the idea leaves no trace in the human mind, and in the second case, the idea does not have any social significance for the individual.

In the formula "Struggle for human mind and heart" the relationship between ideas and consciousness is expressed on the basis of Eastern philosophical thinking. An idea becomes a call to action, a motivating force, a guide for action only when it occupies the heart of a person and becomes an integral part of his spiritual and spiritual world. That's why today the main goal of the ideological struggle is to capture the heart of a person through his mind. People's minds and hearts are turning into a testing ground for different ideas - an ideological training ground.

Today, in order to dominate this or that region, it is not necessary to conquer those lands and destroy their inhabitants. After all, it is possible to own any kind of wealth and natural resources with the support of the local population, whose mind and consciousness have been conquered, and whose views and moods have been changed to a "favorable" direction.

Those who tried to spread their un-Islamic ideas in our country had such malicious goals in mind, that is, to mislead the youth, and with their help to divert the country

from its development path. The actions of Wahhabis and "Hizbut Tharir" editors who were "educated" in foreign countries to poison the minds of our youth can be evaluated in the same way.

The generalization and globalization of the world, on the one hand, served the general development, and on the other hand, it had a strong influence on the destruction of national identity, on the consolidation of the spiritual lives of countries, on the formation of a single public spirituality for all nations of the world. started weaving. The rise of globalization destroys the "borders" of the nation and leads to the transformation of the mass spirituality. As a result of this, the customs, traditions, and values inherent in each nation are in danger of "losing" their importance. This creates threats that lead to the spiritual impoverishment of the nation, to turn them into scumbags who do not understand their identity.

No matter how highly we appreciate the positive role of science, technology, and technology achievements in making them the property of the peoples of the world, we cannot ignore the fact that inequality is emerging in this process. On the one hand, this is happening in the economic, socio-political differences between developed countries and less developed countries, or countries that are now on the path of development. and in this way, it leads to the strengthening of the desire to ensure their dominance, the second audience is also intensifying the popularization of their ideas, ideologies and world views through the means of ensuring this dominance.

In this sense, it is a vital necessity for every nation looking forward to the fight against globalization. However, humanity may not be able to stop it completely in the conditions where its rapid pace is affecting the countries of the world and the peoples and nations living in them, and the interaction and dependence of their people is becoming more widespread. Because the process has not only started, but has taken a massive form, it is dragging all the countries of the world and the peoples living in them into its trap. Both the possibility and the possibility of completely "getting rid" of it are decreasing.

"Public spirituality" is fundamentally different from universal spirituality, and it is based on the spirituality of nations and peoples who have economic, political, and military power and are able to exert their influence on the world. the secret never happens naturally, but arises as a result of activities carried out with specific goals and interests in mind. Even the countries with great potential and power and the peoples living in them have not had time to fully realize their potential, or there is development or It occurs as a result of the influence, pressure and, if necessary, moral violence on the countries entering the League and the peoples living in them.

In the last century, very important changes and discoveries took place in the life of a person, without which it is impossible to imagine our current era. According to

experts, progress in human development will continue at a rapid pace even in the 21st century. In this period, there is no doubt that globalization, i.e., the process of development and rapprochement of countries and peoples from the socio-economic point of view, will reach new heights. However, at the same time, we should not forget that this process presents a number of problems and dangers to humanity.

It should be said that the cases of inculcating one's own ideas into the minds of other peoples, forcing others to accept one's own spirituality and culture, which have been happening since time immemorial, have intensified in our time. Only, he radically changed his appearance and methods of influence. Now, ideological threats are being made not as openly as before, but slowly and without noticing?!

According to the analysis of historical scientists, the first people appeared on earth at least one million years ago. This is not a small term. Of course, during the past time, a person has matured and grown in every way. Now, together with material needs, spiritual needs have appeared in the faith, without which it is difficult to imagine our life today. In particular, a person's desire to know his identity is one of these needs. Because today almost all our compatriots are asked, "Who are we in this bright world and what is our secret, where are we going?" Where and how will our place be when humanity enters the new 21st century?" It's natural to think about such questions." In fact, every person who has a certain level of intelligence and understanding should strive to know who he is, choose his own life path, and if necessary, create for himself a "Free and Prosperous Homeland", should try to build a free and prosperous life. Each of our compatriots living in independent Uzbekistan should think and think about these, and not only these, but other questions, problems and goals should always be in the center of our attention. In particular, "How will the 21st century come to the people of Uzbekistan? How much better will people's lives be than yesterday? Do we realize that the path of reform and renewal that we have chosen for ourselves is a very difficult one? Do we have a clear enough idea of what problems, difficulties, and trials we may face on this path?" It is necessary that these thoughts never leave us.

In this sense, the formation of a sense of responsibility for the fate and future of the nation in young people, awareness of the negative consequences of the flow of foreign ideas, fanatical moods, spiritual and cultural activities in the education of will and faith, conscious living skills. , it is necessary to use the power of mass media wisely. It is the demand of today to create a strong and comprehensive system of measures aimed at preventing the emergence of an ideological gap in society, and eliminating the danger of "mass culture" containing spiritual and moral vices. . Protecting the society from various social and spiritual crises, establishing a consistent system of fighting for a healthy lifestyle is also one of the strategic directions of the state and society. Therefore, strengthening of the population's ideological immunity

should not be limited to large-scale cultural and educational activities, but should actually mean the social and spiritual vigilance of the population.

REFERENCES:

1. Azimov, A. A., & Avliyokulov, U. M. (2019). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЭПОХИ АБУ АБДУЛЛАХ РУДАКИ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 560-562.
2. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной азии в IX-X веках. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 104-105).
3. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 66-67).
4. Azimov, A. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL IDEAS OF THE EARLY RENAISSANCE OF THE EAST IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THEIR REFLECTION IN THE VIEWS OF ZAKARIA AR RAZI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 57-62.
5. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ И АРХИТЕКТУРНАЯ ВЗАИМОВЛИЯНИЯ ВОСТОКА И ВОСТОЧНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ С БУХАРОЙ. In *Современные тенденции развития науки и производства* (pp. 33-34).
6. Азимов, А. А. ўғли Рўзиев, АШ (2022, December). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КНИГИ АВЕСТА. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 37-42).
7. ВЗГЛЯДЫ РУДАКИ О ВОСПИТАНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА АА Азимов - *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2023 515-523
8. SCIENCE, LITERATURE AND POETRY IN TRANSOXIANA AND KHORASAN IX-X CENTURIES.
9. АА Abdullayevich - *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE*, 2023 247-260
10. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (2015). Дипломатические и торговые связи Бухары с Россией XVI–XVIII вв. *Молодой учёный*, 20, 548.
11. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (1994). Рабочая кооперация Узбекистана в 20-е-начале 30-х гг.
12. Atoyev, J. H., & Saloxov, A. Q. (2022). KONSTITUTSIYADA OILA HUQUQI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(TSTU Conference 2), 637-640.

13. Salokhov, A. Q. (2023). METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING THE IDEAS OF BUKHARA NOVELTY IN FORMING TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(8), 171-178.
14. Салохов, А. К. К АНАЛИЗУ ИДЕЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ ТУРКЕСТАНСКОГО ДЖАДИДИЗМА В КОНТЕКСТЕ ЕЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ МИРЗО УЛУҒБЕК НОМИДАГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МИЛЛИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИ МОНИТОРИНГ, 464.
15. Салохов, А. Қ. БУХОРО МАЪРИФАТПАРВАРЧИЛИГИНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ.
16. Murodov, S. A. (2022). Relationship between the universe and man in the works of Fariduddin Attor. In *International conference: problems and scientific solutions* (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 35-41).
17. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. *Актуальные исследования*, 51.
18. Муродов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», *Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал*. Тошкент, 273-276.
19. Мурадов, С. А. кизи Касимова, ФФ (2022, December). ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДИЗАЙНА: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 51-59).
20. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Аттара на бытие. *Международный журнал прикладных исследований*. ИДЖАР, 6(6), 34-36.
21. МУРАДОВ, С. А. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ФАРИДУДДИНА АТТОРА. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый, 51, 529-531.
22. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).
23. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).

24. Мурадов, С. А. (2023, June). ФАРИДУДДИН АТТОР-ВЕЛИКИЙ ШЕЙХ ВОСТОКА. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 149-160).
25. Muradov, S. A. (2023). THE MAIN IDEAS OF THE FOUNDER OF THE GERMAN SCHOOL OF PHILOSOPHY. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 588-594.
26. Sanjar, M. One of the Factors of Purity of the Heart is Futuwat. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 98-101.
27. Sanjar, M. (2020). The views of Fariduddin Attar on being. International journal of applied research. IJAR, 6(6), 34-36.
28. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.
29. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.
30. UMAROVNA, N. N. Four basis analysis of human perfection in the work of Yusuf Khamadani, Odoobi tariqat. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 7(4), 1-3.
31. Nurmatova N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijdivani’s work “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni”/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal //Volume. – Т. 7. – С. 417-420.
32. Djuraev A. et al. Cotton increase the efficiency of cleaning as a result of improving the unit for cleaning small and large wastes //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2023. – Т. 2789. – №. 1.
33. Нурматова, Нигора, and Нодиржон Сафоев. "ШКОЛА СУФИЗМА ЮСУФА ХАМАДОНИ В БУХАРЕ." INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE. Vol. 2. No. 15. 2023.
34. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.
35. Nurmatova, N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijdivani’s work “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni”/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal. Volume, 7, 417-420.

36. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of
37. Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.
38. Нурматова Н. У. Юсуф Ҳамадоний ва хожагон-нақшбандия таълимотининг “назар бар қадам” рашҳаси //Zamonaviy oliy ta’lim: muammo va yechimlar. Xalqaro ilmiy konferensiya. Navoiy. – 2022. – С. 30-31.
39. Jahongir, S. (2020). Philosophical views of Umar life. *Academicia. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.*—India, 10(4), 360-364.
40. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International engineering journal for research & development.*-India, 5(3), 143-148.
41. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Interpretation of the image of may in the ruba of Umar Khayyam. *Monografia pokonferencyjna science, research, development*, 33, 2020-30.
42. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём фалсафий қарашларида инсон тақдири ва эркин ирода масаласи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 2, 197-204.
43. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг асосий асарлари ва рубоийларининг тузилиши, мазмуни ва таҳлили. *Илм Сарчашмалари.*-Урганч, 10, 44-47.
44. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём рубоийларининг талқин ва тавсифи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 9, 206-210.
45. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг ижтимоий-ахлоқий қарашлари. *Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ.*—Тошкент, 3, 107-110.
46. Shodiev, J. (2021). The problem of knowledge in the philosophical views of Umar Khayyam. *Imam al-Bukhari IBS Journal*, 2.
47. Шодиев, Ж. (2022). Илк уйғониш даврида—комил инсонни шакллантириш ватарбиялашда тасаввуф таълимотининг ўрни. *Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi—2022-yil_4-сон*, 229.
48. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Мамлакатимизда инсон қадрини юксалтиришнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий масалалари. *Қарду хабарлари. Илмий-назарий, услубий журнал. Махсус сон (Ижтимоий фанлар).*
49. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). INTERPRETATION AND DESCRIPTION OF UMAR KHAYYAM RUBAYA. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(9), 206-211.
50. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). AGAINST IGNORANCE-FIGHTING WITH ENLIGHTENMENT THE MAIN CRITERIA IN IMPROVING HUMAN VALUE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.

51. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). ATTITUDE TO HUMAN DIGNITY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TEMUR AND TEMURIDS DYNASTY. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(5), 43-47.
52. Shodiyev, J. (2021). JAMIYATDAGI MEHNAT MUNOSABATLARI SHAROITIDA MA'NAVIY SALOHİYAT. Журнал истории и общества, (2)
53. SHODIEV, J. (2021). SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN THE PERIOD OF UMAR KHAYAM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 1(1).
54. Shodiyev, J. (2021). O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOİY-SIYOSIY KOMMUNIKATSIYA RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SIYOSATI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2), 409-416.
55. Shodiyev, J. J. (2020). U THE QUESTION OF HUMAN DESTINY AND FREE IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF OMAR KHAYYAM. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(2), 197-202.
56. Shodiev Jahongir Jurakulovich. Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development 2020/4/16.
57. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). The role of the national idea in increase of human values. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(10), 1160-1164.
58. Shodiyev Jahongir Jo'raqulovich. Inson qadri va uning huquqlari eng oliy qadriyat: tarixiy-huquqiy meros. Ilm sarchashmalari/ Urganch – 3.2023. 19-21.
59. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF SCIENTIFIC THINKING AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT IN IMPROVING HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND VALUE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(9), 251-261.
60. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN INCREASE OF HUMAN VALUES. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 616-625.
61. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF SAGES ON HUMAN VALUES AND GLORIFYING HIM. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(16), 229-238.
62. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2023, June). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В СОЗДАНИИ ФУНДАМЕНТА ТРЕТЬЕГО ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В УКРЕПЛЕНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 124-130).
63. JJ Shodiev. [A STEP TOWARDS HUMAN DIGNITY](#). GOLDEN BRAIN 1 (24), 59-67.

64. Музафаровна, А.М. (2022). СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННАЯ РЕФОРМА И ВОЗНИКАЮЩИЕ КОНФЛИКТЫ. Международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал Galaxy , 10 (5), 623-626.
65. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Интернационализация профессионального образования как требование времени. Молодой ученый, (2), 506-509.
66. Алимова, М. М. (2022, December). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННЕЙ МОТИВАЦИЕЙ РАБОТНИКОВ НА БЕЗОПАСНЫЙ ТРУД И ВЫПОЛНЕНИЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЙ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 43-50).
67. Muzafarovna, A. M., & Tangrievich, M. B. (2021). FORCED COLLECTIVIZATION OF AGRICULTURE IN ZARAFSHAN OASIS (1928-1932). Thematics Journal of Education, 6(November).
68. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Перспективы использования технологии сотрудничества в процессе подготовки педагога профессионального образования. Молодой ученый, (12), 839-841.
69. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Психологические основы педагогического проектирования. Молодой ученый, (12), 837-839.
70. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Социально-психологические факторы формирования модели педагога в современном образовательном процессе. Молодой ученый, (2), 504-506.
71. Алимова, М. М. (2023). «РАСКРЕПОЩЕНИЕ» ЖЕНЩИН В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ (1920-1930 г. г). Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(8), 535-541.
72. Алимова, М. М., & Гариев, А. (2023). ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИЕ КОРРУПЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 261-270.
73. Бафоев Ф. М. Историческая память в мировой политике. Роль ООН и других международных организаций //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2017. – №. 1-4. – С. 180-182.
74. Бафоев Ф. М. ПРИНЦИП НЕДЕЛИМОСТИ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2018. – №. 1-1. – С. 51-54.
75. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. О ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ, РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПРОДОВОЛЬСТВЕННОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований". – №. 21. – С. 53-55.

76. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К ВОПРОСУ КОРРЕКТИРОВКИ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ «МИРОВАЯ ПОЛИТИКА» В КОНТЕКСТЕ СИНЕРГЕТИКИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. – С. 31.
77. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К вопросу о динамике современных международных отношений //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований",(20). – 2022. – С. 35-37.
78. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество, 8(1), 71-73.
79. Каримов, Б.К. (2021). Гармония разума и духа. Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании , 3 (05), 230–234.
80. Каримов, Б. (2023). ПРОЦЕССЫ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ В ДОКУМЕНТАХ ГЕНЕРАЛЬНОЙ АССАМБЛЕИ ООН (2017-2019). MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 291-301.
81. Каримов, Б.К. (2023). СУЩНОСТЬ СОЗНАНИЯ И ЕГО ГЕНЕЗ. Инновационное развитие в образовательной деятельности , 2 (7), 532-539.
82. Aminovna, V. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. Thematics Journal of Education, 6(November).
83. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРАВОВАЯ И РЕЛИГИОЗНАЯ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ В ПЕРИОД ПЕРВОГО РЕНЕССАНСА ВОСТОКА. МОДЕЛИ И МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ , 2 (24), 271-279.
84. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРИОРИТЕТЫ МОЛОДЕЖНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 524-531.
85. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ЁШЛАРНИ БАҒРИКЕНГЛИК РУҲИДА ТАРБИЯЛАШДА ИЖТИМОЙ ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU Conference 2), 232-240.
86. Аминовна, Б. Г. (2022). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ПУТЕЙ СВЯЗИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ КОРОЛЕВСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ ТОРГОВЛИ. Web of Scientist: Международный научный исследовательский журнал, 3, 10-12.
87. Шукриллаев, Ю. А. (2006). Бухоро амирлигида кўшин ва ғарбий иш (1756-1920 йиллар). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий дражасини олиш учун езилган диссертация.
88. Шукуруллаев, Ю. (2022, December). СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЕННЫХ УСТАВНЫХ ГРУПП ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ТИПА В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ.

In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 42-51).

89. Шукруллаев, Ю. А. Армия Бухарского эмирата и военное дело (1756-1920 гг.). Автореферат кандидатской диссертации по истории.-Ташкент, 2006.-26 с.; К вопросу о дипломатических сношениях между Россией и Бухарой через Оренбург в конце XVIII-начале XIX веков. Общественные науки в Узбекистане.-1962, 7, 55-59.

90. Shukrullayev, Y. A. The Army of Bukhara Emirate and Military Affairs (1756-1920). Synopsis of candidate dissertation in history.-Tashkent, 2006.-26 pp.; On the Issue of Diplomatic Relations between Russia and Bukhara through Orenburg at the End of the XVIII-th-the Beginning of the XIX-th Centuries. Social Sciences in Uzbekistan.-1962, 7, 55-59.

91. Shukrullayev, Y. A., & Bahritdinovna, S. R. (2023). GERMANIYA FEDERATIV RESPUBLIKASI IQTISODIYOTINI TIKLASH HARAKATI.“IQTISODIY MO ‘JIZA”. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 577-587.

92. Shukrullayev, Y. A. (2022). FRANSIYA–O ‘ZBEKISTON ALOQALARINING TARIXIY ILDIZLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(3), 110-113.

93. Шукуриллаев, Ю. (2023). ВОЕННЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ ПОД ПРОТЕКТОРАТОМ. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(16), 249-260.

94. Шукуриллаев, Ю. А. (2023). БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИДА ҚЎШИН ТАРКИБИГА ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШ ҚОЙДАЛАРИ, АСКАРЛАРНИНГ ҚЎШИН ТАРКИБИДАН ҚОЧИШИ (ДЕЗЕРТИРСВО), САБАБИ ВА ОҚИБАТЛАРИ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(8), 513-524.

95. Shukurillayev, Y. (2023). Sherbachus and Afghan Groups in the Emirate of Bukhara. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 2(1), 34-36.

96. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 461-463.

97. Mavlonova, I., Akhmetjanov, M., Vokhidova, M., Fayziev, S., & Shokirova, S. (2022, December). Experimental studies of the dynamics of the proposed design of the presser foot with an additional conical spring. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 2373, No. 2, p. 022047). IOP Publishing.

98. Vohidova, M. (2023). SOCIAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS OF THE EXISTENCE OF TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(6), 559-566.

99. Вахидова, М. Т., & Мирзаев, У. Т. (2022, December). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ.

In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 52-62).

100. Вахидова, М. Т. (2022). ДУХОВНО-НРАВСТВЕННОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В КОНТЕКСТЕ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 82-90.

101. Султонова, Л. С. (2023). ИЖТИМОЙ-ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК ИННОВАЦИЯ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ФАОЛИЯТНИНГ УЗВИЙЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU Conference 2), 633-639.

102. Sultonova, L. (2023). Upbringing Mature Person. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 4(3), 71-73.

103. Султанова, Л. С. (2023). ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПОДРОСТОЯЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 557-564.

104. Султонова, Л. С. (2022). МЕСТО ИНЖЕНЕРНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 1(6), 29-34.